

RESPONSE OF SORGHUM CULTIVARS TO RATOON NITROGEN MANAGEMENT UNDER SUMMER CONDITION

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Abstract

The present investigation entitled “Response of sorghum [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench] cultivars for ratoon nitrogen management” was conducted at Post Graduate Institute Research Farm, Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri, Dist. Ahmednagar (Maharashtra) during summer, 2020. The objective of the experiment was to study the effect of ratoon nitrogen management on growth, yield, and quality of forage sorghum cultivars as well as response of cultivars under summer condition.

The experiment was laid out in a split plot design with three replications and sixteen treatment combinations consist Forage sorghum cultivars (4 cultivars) i.e. V₁- Ruchira, V₂- Phule Amruta, V₃- Phule Godhan, V₄- M35-1 and Nitrogen Management (4 nitrogen levels) i.e. N₁- Absolute control, N₂-75% N of RDN, N₃- 100% N of RDN, and N₄- 125% N of RDN for ratoon.

In the present study, forage sorghum cultivar Phule Godhan recorded maximum growth parameters also significantly higher growth and yield attributes viz., plant height, number of leaves plant⁻¹, leaf : stem ratio, green forage yield (82.59 tonne ha⁻¹) and dry matter yield (30.42 tonne ha⁻¹) of forage sorghum. However, 125% N of RDN recorded significantly maximum growth and yield attributes, viz., plant height, number of leaves plant⁻¹, leaf : stem ratio, green forage yield (74.09 tonne ha⁻¹) and dry matter yield (27.55 tonne ha⁻¹).

Key words: Sorghum, cultivars, in vitro dry matter digestibility, total ash, crude protein, crude fibre, , nitrogen levels and ratoon.

Introduction

Sorghum [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench] is the king of millets which is known as great millet, jowar or millo belong to a grass family poaceae. It is one of the important food, feed, fodder and ration for humanity, cattle and poultry. It contains about 10-12 % protein, 70 % carbohydrate and 3 % fat. The livestock population in India is about 535.78 million. Livestock is the backbone of agricultural economy and its importance for Maharashtra cannot be over emphasized. In spite of large livestock population of the state 33 million, (Anonymous, 2019), the production of milk continues to be exceedingly low. Inadequate and poor quality feed and fodder supplied to the milch animals is the main cause of low milk production. There is an urgent need to boost the production of good quality fodder for improving the health of the vast livestock population of the state.

The plant nutrition may not only affect the production of forage but also improve the quality of forage from view point of its protein contents. Fertilizers are most important in the present system of agriculture. Scientific use of fertilizer assumes vital importance in sustainable agriculture. Fertilizers pay back more profit per unit investment. Judicious use of fertilizer is an important management practice to increase the forage sorghum production. Nitrogen is one of the most important plant nutrients required for crop production and is required in large quantities (Balasubramanian *et al.*, 2010). It is the main constituent of amino acid which is directly related to crude protein yield (Almodares *et al.*, 2009). Protein supply is one of the major factor that influences the productivity of animals to build assets and increase livestock productivity in term of yield and quality. High levels of protein feeding may be effective in promoting swift weight gains and milk yield (Hoffman *et al.*, 2001).

Sorghum can be developed as a second sorghum crop (ratoon). Ratooning in sorghum is one of the way to increase productivity. Ratoon is nodal buds of stubble that grows from cutting stem after the main crop harvested and then cultivated again. Cutting the stem in ratoon sorghum aims to simulate shoots and roots so that it can enhance the number of buds and leaves (Mekbib, 2009). Sorghum crops are suitable for the ratooning system because sorghum has a root system that can support the growth and development of sorghum plants up to two- or three-times ratoon (House, 1985).

The present study was therefore planned with the object to determine the effects of nitrogen levels for obtaining maximum fodder yield and quality of sorghum ratoon in summer condition.

Material And Methods

A field experiment was conducted at Post Graduate Institute Instructional Farm, Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri, Dist. Ahmednagar (Maharashtra) during summer, 2020. The experiment was laid out in a split plot design with three replications and sixteen treatment combinations consist Forage sorghum cultivars (4 cultivars) i.e. V₁- Ruchira, V₂- Phule Amruta, V₃- Phule Godhan, V₄- M35-1 and Nitrogen Management (4 nitrogen levels) i.e. N₁- Absolute control, N₂-75% N of RDN, N₃- 100% N of RDN, and N₄- 125% N of RDN for ratoon. The soil of experimental field was clay in texture with a pH of 8.45, organic carbon 0.58 per cent, low in available nitrogen (180.95 kg ha⁻¹), medium in available phosphorus (25.21 kg ha⁻¹) and very high in available potassium (495.20 kg ha⁻¹). The recommended fertilizer dose of forage sorghum was 100:50:40 kg NPK ha⁻¹. The full dose of P₂O₅ and K₂O was applied at the time of sowing. The nitrogen was applied @ 100 kg ha⁻¹, out of that 50 kg nitrogen ha⁻¹ was applied at the time of sowing and remaining 50 kg N ha⁻¹ was applied after 30 DAS. The 50% nitrogen had been given for ratoon after 1st cut and remaining had given after 30 days of 1st cut. The source of nitrogen was urea while the source of phosphorus was single super phosphate. Similarly, potassium was applied through muriate of potash. Forage sorghum was harvested as per the treatment i.e. 60 days after first cut. The green forage yield of forage sorghum was recorded at the time ratoon harvesting. The harvested forage sorghum plants were dried to reduce moisture content. The *in vitro* dry matter digestibility was estimated by Tilley and Terry (1963) method using goat rumen liquor and crude protein, crude fibre contents according to standard method (A.O.A.C, 2005), was carried out.

Results And Discussion**Green Forage Yield**

Data about green forage yield of forage sorghum cultivars as influenced by different nitrogen levels and forage sorghum cultivars are presented in Table 1 and graphically depicted in Fig. 1. The mean green forage yield was 60.10 kg plot⁻¹ and 66.76 tonne ha⁻¹ respectively.

Table 1. Green forage yield of forage sorghum cultivars as influenced periodically by different treatment

Treatment	1 st cut		Ratoon	
	Green fodder yield (kg plot ⁻¹)	Green fodder yield (tonne ha ⁻¹)	Green fodder yield (kg plot ⁻¹)	Green fodder yield (tonne ha ⁻¹)
A) Forage sorghum cultivars				
V ₁ – Ruchira	50.43	56.83	55.37	60.88

V ₂ - Phule Amruta	62.15	69.40	67.06	75.02
V ₃ - Phule Godhan	71.42	78.76	74.52	82.59
V ₄ - M-35-1	39.46	39.47	43.49	48.53
SE m(±)	-	-	1.86	2.19
C.D (P = 0.05)	-	-	6.43	7.57
B) Nitrogen levels				
N ₁ - Absolute control	-	-	52.41	58.05
N ₂ - 75% N of RDN	-	-	57.80	64.41
N ₃ - 100% N of RDN	-	-	63.80	70.48
N ₄ - 125% N of RDN	-	-	66.94	74.09
SE m(±)	-	-	1.09	1.27
C.D (P = 0.05)	-	-	3.17	3.72
C) Interaction				
SE m(±)	-	-	2.17	2.55
C.D (P = 0.05)	-	-	6.34	7.44
General mean	55.86	61.12	60.10	66.76

Effect of forage sorghum cultivars

Green forage yield of ratoon was significantly increased due to different forage sorghum cultivar. The sorghum cultivar Phule Godhan produced significantly highest green forage yield of ratoon (74.52 kg plot⁻¹ and 82.59 tonne ha⁻¹) respectively than the rest of cultivars followed by Phule Amruta, Ruchira and M35-1. Significantly lowest green forage yield of ratoon was recorded by forage sorghum cultivar M35-1 (43.49 kg plot⁻¹ and 48.53 tonne ha⁻¹) respectively. This was might be due to photosynthetic efficiency of a plant to convert its photosynthates into production by integrated effects of genetic makeup of cultivars and growing condition of a crop.

Effect of nitrogen levels

Green forage yield was significantly increased linearly with increased nitrogen levels. Forage sorghum received with 125 % N of RDN ha⁻¹

has produced significantly maximum green forage yield (66.94 kg plot⁻¹ and 74.09 tonne ha⁻¹) and it was at par with application of 100 % N of RDN ha⁻¹ (63.80 kg plot⁻¹, 70.48 tonne ha⁻¹) respectively, followed by 75 % N of RDN ha⁻¹ (57.80 kg plot⁻¹, 64.41 tonne ha⁻¹). Similarly, significantly minimum green forage yield (52.41 kg plot⁻¹ and 58.05 tonne ha⁻¹) respectively of ratoon was recorded by the control treatment. This may be mainly attributed to improved growth parameters viz., plant height, no. of functional leaves plant⁻¹, leaf : stem ratio. The nitrogen is directly involved in cell division, elongation, formation of nucleotides and coenzymes which resulted in increased meristematic activity and nitrogen is integral part of chlorophyll which plays important role in photosynthesis activity of leaves finally helped to accumulate more biomass.

These results are with conformity those reported by Rathod *et al.*, (2002), Shivdhar *et al.*, (2005) and Jha *et al.*, (2012)

Table 1.1 a. Interaction effect between forage sorghum cultivars and nitrogen levels on green forage yield (kg plot⁻¹) of ratoon

Forage Sorghum Cultivars \ Nitrogen Levels	Nitrogen Levels				Mean
	V ₁	V ₂	V ₃	V ₄	
N ₁	48.06	57.22	64.01	40.37	52.41
N ₂	49.54	67.20	70.99	43.49	57.80
N ₃	60.03	69.95	78.97	44.17	63.28
N ₄	63.84	73.88	84.10	45.92	66.94
Mean	55.37	67.06	74.52	43.49	60.11
SE m(±)	2.17				
C.D (P = 0.05)	6.34				

Table 1.2 b. Interaction effect between forage sorghum cultivars and nitrogen levels on green forage yield (tonne ha⁻¹) of ratoon

Forage Sorghum Cultivars \ Nitrogen Levels	Nitrogen Levels				Mean
	V ₁	V ₂	V ₃	V ₄	
N ₁	53.06	64.70	70.19	44.26	58.05
N ₂	54.32	76.85	77.83	48.64	64.41
N ₃	66.15	77.55	88.30	49.94	70.49
N ₄	70.00	81.01	94.05	51.31	74.09
Mean	60.88	75.03	82.59	48.54	66.76

SE m(±)	2.55
C.D (P = 0.05)	7.44

Interaction

The interaction effects between forage sorghum cultivars and nitrogen levels in respect of green forage yield kg plot⁻¹ and green forage yield tonne ha⁻¹ of forage sorghum cultivars were found to be significant. The interaction effect between forage sorghum cultivar Phule Godhan (V₃) and nitrogen level 125 % N of RDN produced significantly higher green forage yield (84.10 kg plot⁻¹ and 94.04 tonne ha⁻¹) than other treatment combinations and it was at par with

Phule Godhan 100 % N of RDN (78.97 kg plot⁻¹ and 88.30 tonne ha⁻¹) respectively. Similarly, significantly lowest green forage yield of ratoon was produced by the forage sorghum cultivar M35-1 in combination of absolute control (40.37 kg plot⁻¹ and 44.26 tonne ha⁻¹) respectively. Higher green fodder yield due to more number of functional leaves and leaf : stem ratio contributed for higher green forage yield.

Fig. 1. Green forage yield (tonne ha⁻¹) of forage sorghum cultivars as influenced periodically by different treatment.

Conclusion

On the basis of one season experimental findings, it could be concluded that cultivation of forage sorghum cultivar Phule Godhan for ratoon crop found appropriate for achieving higher green forage yield as well as gross monetary returns, net monetary returns from the forage sorghum ratoon during summer season.

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